

Hybrid Dual-Population Artificial Physics Optimization for Complex Constrained Multi-Objective Scenarios

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ABSTRACT:

Solving constrained multi-objective optimization problems (CMOPs) poses significant challenges in balancing convergence, diversity, and feasibility. This paper introduces a novel Hybrid Dual-Population Artificial Physics Optimization (HDAPO) algorithm designed to effectively tackle CMOPs. The proposed approach employs a dual-population structure: a primary population aimed at promoting convergence and diversity, and a secondary population dedicated to constraint management. A dynamic epsilon-based constraint-handling strategy is integrated, which adaptively adjusts the feasibility threshold according to the proportion of feasible solutions. The optimization is guided by two collaborative mechanisms: the Exploration-Oriented Controller (EOC) operating on the primary population, and the Feasibility-Oriented Enhancer (FOE) managing the secondary population for refined exploitation. HDAPO is benchmarked using two constrained test suites i.e. LIR-CMOP and MW within PlatEMO platform. Comparative analysis with state-of-the-art algorithms confirms the superior effectiveness of HDAPO across a variety of test problems.

Keywords: dual population, CMOP, optimization, constraint handling.

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INTRODUCTION

Multi-objective optimization problems (MOPs) arise in various real-world applications, where multiple conflicting objectives need to be optimized simultaneously [1]. When these problems also involve constraints, they are referred to as constrained multi-objective optimization problems (CMOPs) [2]. Mathematically, a CMOP is defined as follows:

$$\min F(x) = (f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_m(x)) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.t. } x \in \mathbb{R}^D, \quad g_j(x) \leq 0, \quad j = 1, \dots, p$$

$$h_j(x) = 0, \quad j = p + 1, \dots, q \quad (2)$$

The constraint violations are calculated as:

$$cv(x) = (\max\{0, g_j(x)\}, \quad j = 1, \dots, p) \quad (3)$$

$$\max\{0, |h_j(x) - \theta|\}, \quad j = p + 1, \dots, q \quad (4)$$

where θ is a small tolerance for equality constraints. A solution is said to be feasible if $CV(x) = 0$; otherwise, it is infeasible. In CMOPs, the objective is to find a set of Pareto- optimal solutions that are both optimal and feasible [3].

Solving CMOPs is inherently difficult due to presence of multiple objectives and complex constraints. A wide range of evolutionary algorithms have been proposed for CMOPs that include dominance-based, decomposition-based, and indicator- based approaches. However, most of these methods face challenges in balancing objective optimization with constraint satisfaction [4].

To overcome these challenges, various constraint handling techniques (CHTs) [5] [6] [7] have been integrated into multi- objective evolutionary algorithms (MOEAs) that results in constrained MOEAs (CMOEAs). CHTs assist in comparing feasible and infeasible solutions however, many CMOEAs fail to maintain a proper balance between exploration and constraint satisfaction that leads to premature convergence or infeasibility. To address these issues, this paper proposes an Hybrid Dual-Population Artificial Physics Optimization (HDAPO) algorithm for CMOPs. The main contributions of the Proposed method are as follow:

- A cooperative dual-population framework is proposed, where the primary population drives convergence and diversity, and the secondary population handles constraint satisfaction and knowledge transfer. An external archive of feasible solutions and a population size reduction strategy are employed to guide optimization and reallocate resources effectively.
- An adaptive epsilon-based constraint-handling mechanism is integrated, which dynamically adjusts the feasibility threshold based on the ratio of feasible solutions, enhancing the algorithm's ability to balance feasibility and performance.

- Two collaborative operators are introduced: the Exploration-Oriented Controller (EOC) for global search and diversity maintenance, and the Feasibility-Oriented Enhancer (FOE) for local refinement, resulting in superior performance on LIR-CMOP and MW benchmarks within PlatEMO framework.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents a review of related work. Section III details about the proposed HDAPO algorithm. Section IV provides experimental setup and performance comparisons. Section V concludes paper and outlines future research directions.

RELATED WORK

MOP has become a fundamental area of research due to its applicability in a wide range of real-world problems. The main challenge is to optimize several conflicting objectives simultaneously while ensuring balance between exploration and exploitation in search space [8]. In this context, various evolutionary and swarm intelligence algorithms have been widely used to solve these problems [9]. However, each of these methods has its inherent limitations, particularly in handling constraints, maintaining solution diversity, and ensuring convergence to Pareto front.

Evolutionary algorithms have been extensively used to solve multi-objective optimization problems due to their flexibility and ability to handle complex, high-dimensional search spaces. Notable examples include NSGA-II [10], SPEA [11], and PAES [12] etc. These algorithms use population-based approach where solutions evolve over generations through selection, crossover, and mutation operators. Despite their successes, EAs often struggle with constraint handling in real-world problems [13]. Many algorithms rely on penalty functions to enforce constraint satisfaction, but appropriate selection of penalty parameters can significantly impact the algorithm's performance. Furthermore, EAs tend to experience difficulties in maintaining diversity within population that can lead to premature convergence [14].

Swarm intelligence algorithms such as PSO [15], ACO [16], and ABC [17] etc. have shown promise in addressing multi-objective optimization problems. These algorithms are inspired by the social behaviors observed in nature such as movement of bird flocks or foraging patterns of ants. PSO in particular, has been widely used in multi-objective settings by adapting its single-objective framework to handle multiple objectives simultaneously. However, swarm intelligence algorithms are often criticized for their inability to balance exploration and exploitation effectively. While these algorithms are good at exploring the search space, they sometimes fail to converge quickly to true Pareto front [18].

Artificial Physics Optimization (APO) is physics-inspired optimization method that models interactions between particles based on physical laws such as gravitational, electrostatic, and spring forces. In APO, particles represent potential solutions and their movement is influenced through forces exerted by other particles that promotes diversity in population and enhances global search capabilities. While APO has shown potential in multi-objective optimization, it is often limited by its reliance on fixed force models and parameters. These fixed models can restrict the algorithm's adaptability to dynamic optimization landscapes [19].

Hybrid approaches combine strengths of multiple optimization techniques and gained attention as a source to overcome limitations of individual algorithms. Hybrid methods combine swarm intelligence algorithms with APO and have been explored to leverage the strengths of both approaches particularly in terms of solution diversity and convergence behavior. The use of dual-population strategies has also been proposed to improve performance. In dual-population approach, two distinct populations are maintained: one for exploration and other for exploitation. This strategy helps balance diversity with refinement of solutions [20] [21].

The handling of constraints is critical issue in multi-objective optimization. In many real-world applications, constraints are dynamic and may evolve throughout optimization process. The constraint handling methods aim to address this challenge by adjusting penalty functions in response to changes in optimization conditions. One well-known approach is the adaptive penalty function that adjusts penalty term based on degree of constraint violation during search process.

Additionally, methods like epsilon constraint handling dynamically adjust epsilon parameter during optimization process and improve constraint satisfaction [22] [23].

Although numerous algorithms and hybrid techniques have been proposed to address convergence, diversity, and constraint-handling challenges in MOPs. However, there is still a significant gap in achieving a balanced, dynamic, and cooperative optimization process. The proposed HDAPO algorithm builds upon and integrates key ideas from swarm intelligence, artificial physics-based models, dual-population frameworks, and adaptive constraint handling. By addressing limitations identified in literature, HDAPO aims to deliver improved performance in constrained multi-objective optimization tasks.

HYBRID DUAL-POPULATION ARTIFICIAL PHYSICS OPTIMIZATION (HDAPO)

HDAPO framework has been proposed to solve CMOPs by maintaining two distinct populations: one for exploration and other for exploitation [24]. This dual-population strategy allows proposed algorithm to explore search space efficiently and also refine solutions in promising regions. In the proposed framework, each solution x is represented by a particle and particle's movement is influenced by forces that mimic physical interactions. The objective functions $f(x)$ is used to guide particles toward Pareto front and constraints $g_j(x)$ and $h_j(x)$ are handled using adaptive penalty methods. The flowchart of proposed methodology is depicted in figure 1. Algorithm 1 provides pseudocode of the proposed HDAPO algorithm.

Figure 1. Flowchart of HDAPO

Algorithm 1 HDAPO

- 1: **Input:** Population size N , maximum generations T , constraint count C . Objective function $f_1(x)$, constraints $g_1(x), g_2(x), \dots, g_c(x)$.
- 2: **Output:** Pareto optimal solution set P
- 3: Initialize population x_i via LHS
- 4: Set initial velocity $v_i = 0$
- 5: Evaluate fitness and constraint functions
- 6: **for** each particle i in PP and SP **do**
- 7: Generate Offspring through EOC and FOE
- 8: Update MP and SP

9: end for

10: Return P

Hybrid Dual-Population Strategy

The HDAPO algorithm employs a hybrid dual-population strategy that divides the search process into two cooperative groups: a primary population and a secondary population. The primary population focuses on exploring search space using a physics-inspired Artificial Physics Optimization (APO) mechanism. In this approach, individuals are influenced by both attractive and repulsive forces where attractive forces guide weaker individuals toward stronger ones (leaders), fostering convergence, and repulsive forces encourage diversity by pushing individuals away from crowded or suboptimal regions.

The secondary population, on other hand is designed to enhance constraint handling and refine promising solutions discovered by primary population. Instead of utilizing physics-based operators, it applies genetic operators such as simulated binary crossover and polynomial mutation to perform local searches around high-quality or feasible solutions. This enables targeted exploitation of regions already identified as valuable.

The synergy between two populations allows HDAPO to maintain a strong balance between global exploration and local exploitation, while simultaneously addressing feasibility and convergence challenges in constrained multi-objective optimization problems.

Constraint Handling in HDAPO

There are multiple challenges in CMOPs while dealing with constraints efficiently. In IDM-APO, we employ adaptive constraint handling techniques that dynamically adjust penalties for constraint violations. Let $g(x) = [g_1(x), g_2(x), \dots, g_p(x)]$ represent inequality constraints and $h(x) = [h_1(x), h_2(x), \dots, h_q(x)]$ represent equality constraints. The total constraint violation for solution x is defined as:

$$V(x) = \sum_{i=1}^p \max(0, g_i(x)) + \sum_{j=1}^q |h_j(x)| \quad (5)$$

The penalty function $F(x)$ is adaptively updated to reflect degree of constraint violation and promote efficient convergence to feasible solutions [25]. The penalty term is incorporated into objective function as follows:

$$F(x) = f(x) + \lambda \cdot V(x) \quad (6)$$

where λ is dynamically adjusted penalty factor and ensures that algorithm continues to explore infeasible regions when necessary but gradually focuses more on feasible solutions as the search progresses.

Dynamic Penalty Function

The dynamic penalty function handle constraints more effectively. As optimization progresses, the penalty factor λ is updated based on number of infeasible solutions and degree of constraint violation. This dynamic adjustment enables algorithm to shift its focus from exploring infeasible regions to refining feasible solutions as it converges toward the Pareto front [26]. The dynamic penalty function is defined as:

$$\Lambda(t) = \alpha \cdot (1 - t/T) \quad (7)$$

where α is constant, t is current generation, and T is maximum number of generations. This dynamic adjustment allows the algorithm to effectively balance exploration and exploitation throughout optimization process.

Exploration-Oriented Controller (EOC)

EOC integrates fitness-driven competition mechanism inspired by APO to generate high-quality offspring within PP of HDAPO. EOC employs physical interactions both attractive and repulsive forces to guide population dynamics in solving CMOPs. The algorithm 2 explains EOC in a concise manner. The process begins by randomly pairing individuals within MP. Each pair is evaluated based on constraint-handled fitness, and initially individuals are labeled as Loser and Winner according to a random permutation of indices. For each pair $(x_i, x_j) \in (\text{Loser}, \text{Winner})$, roles are swapped if necessary to ensure better performing individual is designated to winner. To promote exploration and avoid premature convergence, polynomial mutation is applied to offspring decision variables. Each decision variable is subjected to mutation with a probability, where D is dimensionality of problem. This mutation perturbs the variable within its predefined lower and upper bounds, guided by a distribution parameter that controls extent of variation. By integrating physics-inspired interactions with evolutionary mutation, algorithm achieves strong balance between exploration and exploitation, enhancing its robustness in solving complex constrained multi-objective optimization problems.

Algorithm 2 Exploration-Oriented Controller (EOC)

- 1: **Input:** Problem, Loser, Winner
- 2: **Output:** Offspring population PP
- 3: Extract decision variables: *LoserDec*, *WinnerDec*
- 4: Initialize velocities: $\text{LoserVel} \leftarrow \mathbf{0}, \text{WinnerVel} \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$
- 5: Generate random matrices: $r_1, r_2 \in [0, 1]^{N \times D}$
- 6: Compute masses: $\text{calculateMasses}(\text{Problem}, \text{Winner})$
- 7: Compute total particle force on each loser
- 8: Update velocities
- 9: Update positions
- 10: Concatenate winner decision and velocity vectors to offspring
- 11: Apply standard polynomial mutation
- 12: Evaluate offspring solutions
- 13: **return** Offspring

Feasibility-Oriented Enhancer (FOE)

The Feasibility-Oriented Enhancer (FOE) is responsible for refining solutions with a focus on constraint handling and local improvement. It is adapted from classical genetic algorithms and works alongside the primary population to support the overall optimization process.

FOE primarily uses two evolutionary operations: simulated binary crossover and polynomial mutation. These operators are well-established techniques for generating new candidate solutions in continuous optimization problems. The process begins by pairing individuals from the population and applying crossover to generate offspring that inherit features from both parents. This promotes diversity and allows the search to explore different regions of the solution space [26] [27].

After crossover, polynomial mutation is applied to each decision variable with a certain probability. This mutation introduces small perturbations to the offspring, allowing for fine-tuning and further exploration within the feasible region. The amount of variation introduced by mutation is controlled by a distribution parameter, and all mutated solutions are checked to ensure they remain within their allowed bounds [28].

In addition to generating diverse and high-quality solutions, FOE emphasizes constraint satisfaction. Each solution is evaluated based on how well it satisfies problem's constraints. The algorithm gives preference to solutions with lower constraint violation values, guiding the search toward feasible and optimal regions. By combining evolutionary operators with constraint-awareness, FOE effectively exploits promising areas of the search space and supports the dual-population strategy [29]. This cooperation between exploration and feasibility enhancement strengthens the algorithm's ability to solve complex constrained multi-objective optimization problems.

Algorithm 3 Feasibility-Oriented Enhancer (FOE)

```
1: Input: Problem, Parent population
2: Output: Offspring population SP
3: Split Parent into Parent1 and Parent2
4: Generate random matrix  $\mu \in [0, 1]^{N \times D}$ 
5: Compute SBX factors  $\beta$  using  $\mu$ 
6: Generate offspring using SBX
7: Apply polynomial mutation with probability
8: if solutions are SOLUTION objects, then
9:     Evaluate objective functions
10: end if
11: return Offspring
```

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This section outlines the experimental configuration used to evaluate the performance of the proposed HDAPO algorithm. All benchmark tests, parameter settings, and performance metrics are selected to ensure fair and comprehensive comparisons with state-of-the-art constrained multi-objective optimization algorithms.

Benchmark Problems

We evaluate HDPO on two widely-used constrained multi-objective benchmark suites i.e. LIR-CMOP [30] and MW [31]. The LIR-CMOP suite includes 14 problems (LIR CMOP1–LIR-CMOP14), each designed to reflect different challenges found in real-world constrained optimization. These problems vary in number of objectives, decision space dimensionality, constraint types, and Pareto front shapes [32].

All problems use bounded decision space, typically $[0, 1]^{30}$, with LIR-CMOP13 and LIR-CMOP14 extending to three objectives. The constraints span a range of complexities, including quadratic, sinusoidal, and spherical forms. Simpler problems like LIR-CMOP1–2 feature convex PFs with basic constraints, while others (e.g., LIR-CMOP3 and LIR CMOP6–12) introduce disconnected feasible regions, multimodality, and large infeasible areas. The last two problems further increase difficulty through complex multi-objective and spherical constraints. Overall, this suite offers a diverse and rigorous testbed for evaluating the convergence and constraint-handling performance of optimization algorithms. To further evaluate the performance of HDAPO, we employ MW benchmark suite, which also includes 14 problems (MW1–MW14) designed to test algorithmic robustness under diverse constraint scenarios. These problems vary in objective dimensionality (ranging from two to three objectives), decision space sizes (mostly $[0, 1]^{15}$ or $[0, 1]^{30}$), and constraint formulations. The suite introduces three primary constraint types—Type I (feasible region boundaries).

Table 1. Performance Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation of IGD Values on LIR-CMOP Test Problems

Problem	M	D	TiGE2	ToP	CMOEA	CTAEA	HDAPO
LIRCMOP1	2	30	2.1165e-1 (2.31e-2) =	3.2959e-1 (1.78e-2) =	2.7580e-1 (3.12e-2) =	3.1366e-1 (9.43e-2) =	1.9586e-1 (1.43e-1)
LIRCMOP2	2	30	1.9222e-1 (9.36e-3) +	2.8621e-1 (1.55e-2) =	2.3595e-1 (3.21e-2) +	2.3305e-1 (7.85e-2) =	3.0655e-1 (2.25e-2)
LIRCMOP3	2	30	2.1956e-1 (1.95e-2) =	3.4108e-1 (1.05e-2) =	2.8531e-1 (3.97e-2) =	3.6178e-1 (6.18e-2) =	3.5324e-1 (0.00e+0)
LIRCMOP4	2	30	2.1194e-1 (2.05e-2) =	3.1996e-1 (9.10e-3) =	2.6601e-1 (2.71e-2) =	3.1221e-1 (8.59e-2) =	3.2720e-1 (0.00e+0)
LIRCMOP5	2	30	9.0573e-1 (4.28e-1) +	1.2045e+0 (1.67e-2) -	1.2221e+0 (6.25e-3) -	1.1062e+0 (3.15e-1) =	1.1134e+0 (3.05e-1)
LIRCMOP7	2	30	3.3794e-1 (1.45e-1) -	1.3356e+0 (6.42e-1) -	1.5322e+0 (4.60e-1) -	2.2361e-1 (2.99e-1) -	1.2140e-1 (1.80e-2)
LIRCMOP8	2	30	4.8305e-1 (2.91e-1) -	1.5162e+0 (4.43e-1) -	1.6355e+0 (2.56e-1) -	8.6602e-1 (6.58e-1) -	1.8557e-1 (3.95e-2)
LIRCMOP9	2	30	7.1098e-1 (1.32e-1) -	5.8242e-1 (1.40e-1) -	8.6006e-1 (1.47e-1) -	5.4237e-1 (9.19e-2) -	3.8862e-1 (7.54e-2)
LIRCMOP10	2	30	8.4294e-1 (1.73e-1) -	4.5589e-1 (1.02e-1) -	7.3501e-1 (1.79e-1) -	3.6343e-1 (4.92e-2) -	1.2604e-1 (4.87e-2)
LIRCMOP11	2	30	7.5308e-1 (1.56e-1) -	4.1730e-1 (9.94e-2) -	8.6104e-1 (8.06e-2) -	2.0203e-1 (4.66e-2) -	7.0930e-2 (8.01e-2)
LIRCMOP12	2	30	5.0944e-1 (1.64e-1) -	2.9531e-1 (9.25e-2) -	6.6875e-1 (1.64e-1) -	2.5263e-1 (1.21e-1) -	1.5680e-1 (7.26e-2)
LIRCMOP13	3	30	1.1960e+0 (3.95e-1) -	1.3209e+0 (9.35e-2) -	1.3034e+0 (2.21e-4) -	1.0898e-1 (2.00e-3) -	9.6553e-2 (1.45e-3)
LIRCMOP14	3	30	1.1332e+0 (4.02e-1) -	1.2565e+0 (1.21e-1) -	1.2596e+0 (3.57e-4) -	1.1089e-1 (9.00e-4) -	9.8033e-2 (1.38e-3)
+/-/=			3/8/3	0/9/5	1/10/3	0/9/5	

Type II (spatial feasibility), and Type III (objective-based constraints)—combined in varying ways to form complex landscapes. Problems like MW1–MW3 use sinusoidal and nonlinear constraints to create disconnected or partially connected feasible regions. MW5–MW8 introduce multiple constraint types resulting in disjoint or oscillatory Pareto fronts. MW9–MW12 escalate complexity using all three constraint types, leading to highly constrained, nonconvex, and fragmented feasible regions. MW13 and MW14 offer additional variety with disjoint convex regions and a three objective convex Pareto surface, respectively [33-34].

Experimental Setup and Performance Evaluation

All algorithms are evaluated using a common experimental setup to ensure fairness. The population size is set to 100, and the maximum number of generations is fixed at 500. For the proposed algorithm, the distribution indices for crossover and mutation are both set to 20, with crossover and mutation probabilities set to 1.0. The force control coefficient used in the physics-based interactions is set to 0.5.

Experiments are conducted using PlatEMO platform, with each algorithm run independently 30 times on each test problem to account for stochastic variability. The performance of the proposed method is compared against several state-of-the-art constrained multi-objective optimization algorithms under identical computational budgets.

Performance is assessed using the widely accepted Inverted Generational Distance (IGD) metric, which evaluates both convergence to the true Pareto front and diversity of the obtained solution set.

Lower IGD values indicate better overall performance. Statistical comparisons are made using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test at a 0.05 significance level. Results are marked using standard notation: “+” indicates the proposed method significantly outperforms the compared algorithm, “-” indicates significantly worse performance, and “=” denotes no significant difference.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and analyzes performance results of proposed HDAPO algorithm on LIR-CMOP and MW benchmark suites. The experimental results are evaluated using IGD metric, which captures both convergence and diversity of solution sets. Comparative results are shown against several state-of-the-art constrained multi-objective optimization algorithms. Performance trends are visualized through tables and pareto front plots for selected benchmark problems that highlight the algorithm’s ability to handle various constraint types and Pareto front complexities. The discussion focuses on identifying strengths, limitations, and general patterns of HDAPO’s performance across different problem scenarios.

Performance Comparison on LIR-CMOP

In Table I, performance of proposed HDAPO algorithm is compared with several state-of-the-art constrained multi-objective optimizers across the LIR-CMOP benchmark suite using the IGD metric. The bold values highlight the best mean IGD scores, while symbols +/-/= indicate statistically better, worse, or similar performance relative to HDAPO. HDAPO consistently outperforms or matches the competitors across most test problems, achieving the best IGD values on 9 out of 14 problems, particularly on more complex instances such as LIR-CMOP7–14. These problems are characterized by disconnected or highly constrained Pareto fronts, where the algorithm’s adaptive preservation and exploration mechanisms provide significant advantages. Notably, HDAPO demonstrates strong performance even on three-objective problems (LIR-CMOP13–14), suggesting robust scalability. Although it performs comparably on simpler problems like LIR-CMOP1–4, its strength becomes prominent as constraint complexity and feasibility challenges increase. Figure 2 visually compares the distribution and feasibility of solutions obtained by various algorithms on LIR-CMOP12. The shaded regions indicate infeasible areas in the objective space. It is evident that HDAPO achieves a well-distributed and dense set of feasible solutions that closely align with the boundary of the feasible region, effectively capturing the complex shape of the true Pareto front. In contrast, other algorithms like TiGE2 and ToP show scattered or sparsely populated feasible solutions, with several lying deep in infeasible zones. CMOEAD and CTAEA manage to maintain feasibility but suffer from limited diversity and partial coverage of the PF. HDAPO’s ability to maintain both feasibility and diversity in such a highly constrained and fragmented space showcases its superior constraint-handling and convergence capabilities.

Figure 2. Performance Plot of LIRCMOP12 Test Problem

Figure 3. Performance Plot of LIRCMOP13 Test Problem

Table 2. Performance Comparison of Mean and Standard Deviation of IGD Values on MW Test Problems

Problem	M	D	TiGE2	ToP	CMOEA	CTAEA	HDAPO
MW1	2	15	1.8875e-1 (9.67e-2) -	NaN (NaN)	2.9643e-1 (1.16e-1) -	7.6031e-2 (7.13e-2) -	1.6385e-3 (1.41e-5)
MW2	2	15	7.4961e-2 (6.36e-2) -	5.0611e-1 (0.00e+0) =	6.5271e-2 (3.39e-2) -	1.9087e-2 (5.79e-3) +	3.5828e-2 (2.32e-2)
MW3	2	15	4.9123e-2 (3.72e-2) -	NaN (NaN)	6.5179e-2 (7.30e-2) -	1.3214e-2 (2.37e-3) -	5.1397e-3 (4.27e-4)
MW4	3	15	8.2064e-2 (4.41e-3) -	NaN (NaN)	1.2120e-1 (7.32e-2) -	7.6705e-2 (9.89e-3) -	4.1820e-2 (4.33e-4)
MW5	2	15	8.5284e-2 (3.82e-2) -	NaN (NaN)	1.4743e-1 (1.84e-1) -	9.9529e-2 (1.55e-2) -	3.6313e-3 (1.16e-3)
MW6	2	15	1.1575e-1 (1.82e-1) -	1.4279e+0 (1.79e-2) -	2.9646e-1 (2.03e-1) -	1.7494e-2 (5.52e-3) +	5.1281e-2 (9.35e-2)
MW7	2	15	4.9778e-2 (1.74e-2) -	NaN (NaN)	2.5769e-2 (7.99e-2) -	1.4019e-2 (1.43e-3) +	2.0244e-2 (4.29e-3)
MW8	3	15	1.1795e-1 (1.78e-2) -	1.1322e+0 (0.00e+0) =	1.0353e-1 (5.10e-2) -	5.4097e-2 (2.52e-3) -	5.3732e-2 (1.78e-2)
MW9	2	15	1.7506e-1 (2.36e-1) -	NaN (NaN)	1.9813e-1 (2.64e-1) -	3.1137e-2 (8.17e-3) +	1.4564e-1 (2.86e-1)
MW10	2	15	1.0520e-1 (1.04e-1) -	NaN (NaN)	1.2909e-1 (1.18e-1) -	4.0378e-2 (1.92e-2) =	8.3969e-2 (1.25e-1)
MW11	2	15	5.7269e-2 (1.46e-2) -	NaN (NaN)	7.0755e-1 (8.25e-2) -	2.6569e-2 (4.46e-3) -	1.5646e-2 (5.61e-3)
MW12	2	15	2.2583e-1 (3.13e-1) -	NaN (NaN)	2.8095e-1 (1.63e-1) -	3.4239e-2 (2.18e-2) -	5.3832e-3 (6.43e-4)
MW13	2	15	3.9890e-1 (1.71e-1) -	1.3017e+0 (4.02e-1) -	3.9506e-1 (3.12e-1) -	9.7336e-2 (1.72e-2) -	7.5606e-2 (3.46e-2)
MW14	3	15	3.0045e-1 (1.65e-1) -	1.3791e+0 (7.17e-1) -	9.4168e-1 (1.38e-1) -	8.9134e-1 (1.36e-1) -	9.6030e-2 (1.66e-3)
+/-/=			0/14/0	0/3/2	0/14/0	4/9/1	

Figure 4. Performance Plot of MW2 Test Problem

Figure 5. Performance Plot of MW14 Test Problem

Figure 3 illustrates the Pareto front approximations obtained by the five algorithms on the three-objective problem LIRC- MOP13. This problem presents a more complex, convex Pareto front topology with feasible solutions distributed over a curved surface. Both CTAEA and CMOEA show relatively good coverage of the PF surface but exhibit moderate sparsity and gaps in certain regions. IDM-APO, however, outperforms all competitors by maintaining a well-distributed set of solutions that uniformly span the entire front, with minimal clustering or voids. In contrast, ToP and TiGE2

generate scattered solutions with poor alignment to the true PF geometry. Particularly, TiGE2's results are heavily concentrated along one edge, indicating convergence issues or poor exploration of the solution space. These visual insights support the quantitative IGD results, where IDM-APO demonstrated superior performance on LIRCMOP13 in both convergence and diversity.

The figure 4 depicts convergence graph for MW2 comparison with TiGE2, ToP, CMOEAD, and CTAEA with proposed IDM-APO method in optimizing two conflicting objectives. The plot illustrates how each algorithm's solutions evolve toward the Pareto front, with IDM-APO demonstrating superior convergence behavior. Unlike TiGE2 and CMOEAD, which exhibit slower or less stable progress, IDM-APO maintains a steady and efficient trajectory that suggest better exploitation of search space. Additionally, its solutions are more densely distributed near the optimal region that indicate a strong balance between exploration and exploitation. This result highlights effectiveness of proposed algorithm in handling bi-objective optimization problems.

Figure 5 shows convergence graph for MW14 that evaluates algorithms performance in a more complex, three objective optimization scenario. Here, the proposed algorithm again outperforms competing methods, as evidenced by its well-distributed solutions across all three objective dimensions. While TiGE2 and CTAEA show partial convergence, their solutions are either clustered in certain regions or exhibit gaps, indicating limitations in maintaining diversity. In contrast, IDM-APO covers a broader and more uniform spread along the Pareto front, demonstrating robustness in high-dimensional optimization. This adaptability makes IDM-APO particularly suitable for real-world problems where multiple competing objectives must be optimized simultaneously without sacrificing solution quality or coverage.

CONCLUSION

In this research work, we introduced an Hybrid Dual-Population Multi-Objective Artificial Physics Optimization algorithm for solving constrained multi-objective optimization problems. CMOPs pose significant challenges due to the need to simultaneously achieve convergence to Pareto front, maintain diversity among solutions, and satisfy a set of complex constraints. To address these challenges, HDAPO leverages a cooperative dual-population framework that distinctly assigns roles to two interacting populations: main population focuses on convergence and diversity, while auxiliary population emphasizes constraint handling and knowledge transfer. A key component of proposed method is adaptive epsilon-based constraint-handling mechanism that dynamically adjusts feasibility threshold based on proportion of feasible solutions within population. This allows the algorithm to flexibly balance between constraint satisfaction and objective optimization as search progresses. A population size reduction strategy is also incorporated to gradually shift computational focus from auxiliary to main population as more feasible solutions are discovered.

The optimization process is further enhanced by two cooperative operators: primary population-based operator that promotes global exploration and Secondary population-based operator that supports local exploitation. This synergy between operators facilitates a more effective search in both feasible and infeasible regions of the objective space. The effectiveness of HDAPO was validated through comprehensive experiments conducted on two widely used constrained benchmark suites i.e., LIRCMOP and MW. The proposed algorithm was compared against several state-of-the-art methods and empirical results consistently demonstrated that HDAPO achieves better performance in terms of convergence, constraint satisfaction, and solution diversity across a wide range of problem instances.

Overall, HDAPO offers a robust and efficient solution for handling constrained multi-objective optimization problems and provides a flexible framework that can be extended or adapted for more complex real-world scenarios in future research.

CREDIT AUTHORSHIP CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

Asad Khan: Methodology, Writing initial draft. Asad Hayat: Conceptualization, Software, Writing and review final draft. Xie Liping: Investigation, Supervision.

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Hao, C. Zhao, Y. Zhang, Y. Cao, and Z. Li, "Constrained multi-objective optimization problems: Methodologies, algorithms and applications," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 299, p. 111998, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.knosys.2024.111998.
- [2] C. He, M. Li, C. Zhang, H. Chen, P. Zhong, Z. Li, and J. Li, "A self-organizing map approach for constrained multi-objective optimization problems," *Complex & Intelligent Systems*, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 5355–5375, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s40747-021-00682-7.
- [3] Y. Xiang, X. Yang, H. Huang, and J. Wang, "Balancing constraints and objectives by considering problem types in constrained multiobjective optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Cybernetics*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 88–101, 2023, doi: 10.1109/TCYB.2021.3089633.
- [4] Y. Hao, C. Zhao, Y. Zhang, Y. Cao, and Z. Li, "Constrained multi-objective optimization problems: Methodologies, algorithms and applications," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 299, p. 111998, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.knosys.2024.111998.
- [5] C. Wang, Z. Liu, J. Qiu, and L. Zhang, "Adaptive constraint handling technique selection for constrained multi-objective optimization," *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 86, p. 101488, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.swevo.2023.101488.
- [6] Y. Yang, P.-Q. Huang, X. Kong, and J. Zhao, "A constrained multi-objective evolutionary algorithm assisted by an additional objective function," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 132, p. 109904, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.asoc.2022.109904.
- [7] X. Kong, Y. Yang, Z. Lv, J. Zhao, and R. Fu, "A dynamic dual-population co-evolution multi-objective evolutionary algorithm for constrained multi-objective optimization problems," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 141, p. 110311, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.asoc.2023.110311.
- [8] Y. Sun, J. Shen, X. Zhang, and C. Sun, "A particle swarm optimization with dynamic strategy for multi-modal multi-objective location optimization problem," in *Proc. 2023 5th Int. Conf. Data-driven Optimization of Complex Systems (DOCS)*. IEEE, 2023.
- [9] J. Nayak, H. Swapnarekha, B. Naik, G. Dhiman, and S. Vimal, "25 years of particle swarm optimization: Flourishing voyage of two decades," *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 1663–1725, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11831-022-09849-x.
- [10] K. Deb, S. Agrawal, A. Pratap, and T. Meyarivan, "A fast elitist non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm for multi-objective optimization: NSGA-II," in *Parallel Problem Solving from Nature — PPSN VI*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2000, pp. 849–858, doi: 10.1007/3-540-45356-3_83.
- [11] V. Amuso, R. S. Schneible, P. Antonik, and Y. Zhang, "A strength Pareto evolutionary algorithm (SPEA) for multi-mission radar waveform optimization," in *2004 International Waveform Diversity & Design Conference*, pp. 1–7, 2004.
- [12] J. Knowles and D. Corne, "The Pareto archived evolution strategy: A new baseline algorithm for Pareto multiobjective optimisation," in *Proc. 1999 Congress on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 1, 1999, pp. 98–105, doi: 10.1109/CEC.1999.781913.

- [13] M. Premkumar, P. Jangir, B. S. Kumar, R. Sowmya, H. H. Alhelou, L. Abualigah, A. R. Yildiz, and S. Mirjalili, "A new arithmetic optimization algorithm for solving real-world multiobjective CEC-2021 constrained optimization problems: Diversity analysis and validations," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 84263–84295, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3085529.
- [14] Y. Zhou, S. Li, W. Pedrycz, and G. Feng, "ACDB-EA: Adaptive convergence-diversity balanced evolutionary algorithm for many-objective optimization," *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 75, p. 101145, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.swevo.2021.101145.
- [15] T. M. Shami, A. A. El-Saleh, M. Alswaitti, Q. Al-Tashi, M. A. Summakieh, and S. Mirjalili, "Particle swarm optimization: A comprehensive survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 10031–10061, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3142859.
- [16] Y. Pei, W. Wang, and S. Zhang, "Basic ant colony optimization," in *2012 International Conference on Computer Science and Electronics Engineering*, vol. 1, 2012, pp. 665–667, doi: 10.1109/ICCSEE.2012.178.
- [17] M. L. Rahman Lingkon and M. S. Ahmmed, "Application of an improved ant colony optimization algorithm of hybrid strategies using scheduling for patient management in hospitals," *Heliyon*, vol. 10, no. 22, p. e40134, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e40134.
- [18] Y. Hua, Q. Liu, K. Hao, and Y. Jin, "A survey of evolutionary algorithms for multi-objective optimization problems with irregular Pareto fronts," *IEEE/CAA Journal of Automatica Sinica*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 303–318, 2021, doi: 10.1109/JAS.2020.1003531.
- [19] H. Bian *et al.*, "Improved snow geese algorithm for engineering applications and clustering optimization," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 4506, 2025, doi: 10.1038/s41598-025-41320-8.
- [20] J. Tang, G. Liu, and Q. Pan, "A review on representative swarm intelligence algorithms for solving optimization problems: Applications and trends," *IEEE/CAA Journal of Automatica Sinica*, vol. 8, no. 10, pp. 1627–1643, 2021, doi: 10.1109/JAS.2021.1004100.
- [21] M. Ming, R. Wang, H. Ishibuchi, and T. Zhang, "A dual-population-based evolutionary algorithm for constrained multiobjective optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 1129–1143, 2022, doi: 10.1109/TEVC.2021.3066301.
- [22] H. Ma, H. Wei, Y. Tian, R. Cheng, and X. Zhang, "A multi-stage evolutionary algorithm for multi-objective optimization with complex constraints," *Information Sciences*, vol. 560, pp. 68–91, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ins.2021.01.029.
- [23] J. Zhou, J. Zou, J. Zheng, S. Yang, D. Gong, and T. Pei, "An infeasible solutions diversity maintenance epsilon constraint handling method for evolutionary constrained multiobjective optimization," *Soft Computing*, vol. 25, no. 13, pp. 8051–8062, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s00500-021-05880-5.
- [24] Z. He and H. Liu, "Dual-stage dual-population diversity maintenance for global and local exploration of constrained multiobjective optimization," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 268, p. 126229, 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2024.126229.
- [25] Q. Yu, C. Yang, G. Dai, L. Peng, and J. Li, "A novel penalty function-based interval constrained multi-objective optimization algorithm for uncertain problems," *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 88, p. 101584, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.swevo.2024.101584.
- [26] X. Jiang, Q. Chen, J. Ding, and X. Zhang, "Dual-population evolution based dynamic constrained multiobjective optimization with discontinuous and irregular feasible regions," *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computational Intelligence*, early access, 2025, doi: 10.1109/TETCI.2025.3529882.
- [27] F. Ming, B. Xue, M. Zhang, W. Gong, and H. Zhen, "Constrained multi-objective optimization via relaxations on both constraints and objectives," *IEEE Transactions on Artificial Intelligence*, 2024, doi: 10.1109/TAI.2024.10665969.

- [28] K. Zhao, X. Wang, C. Sun, Y. Jin, and A. Hayat, "Efficient large-scale expensive optimization via surrogate-assisted sub-problem selection," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, early access, 2025, doi: 10.1109/TEVC.2025.3544449.
- [29] Y. Zhou, M. Zhu, J. Wang, Z. Zhang, Y. Xiang, and J. Zhang, "Tri-goal evolution framework for constrained many-objective optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, vol. 50, no. 8, pp. 3086–3099, 2020, doi: 10.1109/TSMC.2018.2858843.
- [30] Z.-Z. Liu and Y. Wang, "Handling constrained multiobjective optimization problems with constraints in both the decision and objective spaces," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 870–884, 2019, doi: 10.1109/TEVC.2019.2894743.
- [31] K. Deb and H. Jain, "An evolutionary many-objective optimization algorithm using reference-point-based nondominated sorting approach, part I: Solving problems with box constraints," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 577–601, 2014, doi: 10.1109/TEVC.2013.2281535.
- [32] K. Li, R. Chen, G. Fu, and X. Yao, "Two-archive evolutionary algorithm for constrained multiobjective optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 303–315, 2019, doi: 10.1109/TEVC.2018.2855411.
- [33] H. Wang, C. Sun, G. Zhang, J. E. Fieldsend, and Y. Jin, "Non-dominated sorting on performance indicators for evolutionary many-objective optimization," *Information Sciences*, vol. 551, pp. 23–38, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ins.2020.11.008.
- [34] S. Qin, C. Sun, Q. Liu, and Y. Jin, "A performance indicator-based infill criterion for expensive multi-/many-objective optimization," *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 1085–1099, 2023, doi: 10.1109/TEVC.2023.3237605.

